

Do neutrinos dream in 5D?

Based on **2512.02101**
in collaboration with **D. Pasari** and **J. Turner**

Arturo de Giorgi

8th January 2026

Neutrino Portal to BSM

$$\begin{pmatrix} \nu_L \\ e_L \end{pmatrix} + e_R$$

“old” SM: neutrino are **massless**

Neutrino Portal to BSM

$$\begin{pmatrix} \nu_L \\ e_L \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \nu_R \\ e_R \end{pmatrix}$$

“new” SM? neutrino are **massive**

Neutrino Portal to BSM

$$\begin{pmatrix} \nu_L \\ e_L \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \nu_R \\ e_R \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{gauge singlet}$$

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Extra dimensions?

$$S = \int_{\mathcal{M}} d^4x (\dots) \rightarrow \int_{\mathcal{M}} d^{4+\delta}x (\dots) \quad \delta = 1, 2, \dots$$

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Extra-dimensional Theory

4D-Minkowski

1) $\mathcal{M} = \mathcal{M}_{\text{Minkowski}} \times \mathcal{M}_{\text{rest}}$

2) Extra dimensions must have (small) **finite size** R

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current **gravitational flat** constraints:

$$1/R \gtrsim 10^{-2} \text{ eV} \Leftrightarrow R \lesssim 20 \mu\text{m}$$

Why neutrinos?

Orbifold S_1/\mathbf{Z}_2

3-brane

Bulk
 $\sim R$

3-brane

SM is **localised**
on a 3-brane

K. R. Dienes, E. Dudas, and T. Gherghetta [hep-ph/9811428]

N. Arkani-Hamed, S. Dimopoulos, G. R. Dvali, and J. March-Russell [hep-ph/9811448]

G. R. Dvali and A. Y. Smirnov [hep-ph/9904211]

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Orbifold S_1/\mathbf{Z}_2

SM **gauge singlet** = "right-handed neutrinos"

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Extra dimensions 101

Extra-dimensional Theory

dimensional reduction

A particle **propagating in extra dimensions** is observed as an **infinite tower of massive particle** in the 4D EFT

UV

4D Effective Theory

Kaluza-Klein (KK)
tower

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$$S = \int d^4x \int dy \mathcal{L}(x, y) = \int d^4x \mathcal{L}_{\text{eff}}(x)$$

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orthonormal basis for y
"Wave functions"

Neutrino portal to extra dimensions

$$\Psi(x, y) = \begin{pmatrix} \psi_L(x, y) \\ \psi_R(x, y) \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{bulk}} = i\bar{\Psi}\Gamma^M\nabla_M\Psi - \text{sgn}(y)M_D\bar{\Psi}\Psi - \frac{M_J}{2}\bar{\Psi}\Psi^c$$

$$-\mathcal{L}_{\text{brane}} \supset \bar{L}_L\tilde{Y}_D\tilde{H}\psi_R + \frac{1}{2}\bar{\psi}_R^c\tilde{B}\psi_R + \text{h.c.}$$

M. Carena, Y.-Y. Li, C. S. Machado, P. A. N. Machado, and C. E. M. Wagner [1708.09548]

D. V. Forero, C. Giunti, C. A. Ternes, and O. Tyagi [2207.02790]

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= SM portal

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— **2512.02101** —

comprehensive analysis of **masses, mixings** and
oscillation constraints

Brane Dirac

= SM portal

Brane Majorana

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Brane Dirac

$$1/R \equiv \mu_1 \quad \mu_n = n\mu_1$$

$$\mathcal{L} \supset -\bar{\nu}_L \begin{pmatrix} m_D & \sqrt{2}m_D & \sqrt{2}m_D & \dots & \sqrt{2}m_D \\ 0 & \mu_1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \mu_2 & \dots & 0 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & \mu_N \end{pmatrix} \nu_R$$

Eigenvalues and mixings:

$$\pi \cot \left(\frac{\pi m_\lambda}{\mu_1} \right) = \frac{\mu_1 m_\lambda}{m_D^2}$$

$$\mathcal{N}_\lambda = \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\pi^2 m_D^2}{\mu_1^2} + \frac{m_\lambda^2}{m_D^2} + 1 \right) \right]^{-1/2}$$

Brane Dirac

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Minos: solid

Daya Bay: dashed

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Bulk Majorana

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$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & m_D & m_D & m_D & \dots & m_D & m_D \\ m_D & M_J & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ m_D & 0 & M_J + \mu_1 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ m_D & 0 & 0 & M_J - \mu_1 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ m_D & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & M_J + \mu_N & 0 \\ m_D & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & M_J - \mu_N \end{pmatrix}$$

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Eigen

Minos: solid Daya Bay: dashed

Summary and Conclusions

Neutrinos occupy a *special role* in extra-dimensional physics

Bulk neutrinos can:

- be far **more sensitive than gravitational probes**
- provide **UV origin** for **N-sterile neutrinos** models

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Neutrinos occupy a *special role* in
extra-dimensional physics

Bulk neutrinos

- be far **more**
- provide **UV**

many observables **beyond**
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origin for **sterile neutrinos** models

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Neutrinos occupy a *special role* in extra-dimensional physics

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Thanks

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KK expansion

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KK masses

$$i\bar{\Psi}\Gamma^M\nabla_M\Psi \longrightarrow \text{KK masses} \sim 1/R \equiv \mu_1$$

- Mode $n = 0$ is special: it is always **massless**
- $\mu_1 \gg M$ **decouples** the tower (not the 0-mode)

Extra dimensions 101

KK expansion $\psi(x, y) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{L}} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \psi_n(x) \chi_n(y)$

KK mass

size of μ_1 **interpolates** between **3 and 3N** sterile neutrino scenarios

1

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Model	Extra params.	$\chi_0(\pi R)$	$\chi_n(\pi R)$	KK-masses
Brane Dirac	–	1	$\sqrt{2}$	$n\mu_1$
Bulk Dirac	M_D	$\left[\frac{2\pi R M_D}{(e^{2\pi R M_D} - 1)} \right]^{1/2}$	$\frac{\sqrt{2}\mu_n}{\sqrt{\mu_n^2 + M_D^2}}$	$\sqrt{M_D^2 + (n\mu_1)^2}$
Bulk Majorana	M_J	1	$\sqrt{2}$	$M_J \pm n\mu_1$
Brane Majorana	B	1	$\sqrt{2}$	$\pm n\mu_1$

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Neutrinos Oscillation

flavour - mass basis: $|\nu_{\alpha,n}\rangle = \sum_i \sum_m U_{\alpha i} V_{nm}^i |\hat{\nu}_{i,m}\rangle$

oscillation probability: $P_{\alpha \rightarrow \beta}(t) \equiv |\langle \nu_{\beta,0}(t) | \nu_{\alpha,0}(0) \rangle|^2 = \left| \sum_{in} (U_{\alpha i} V_{0n}^i) (U_{\beta i} V_{0n}^i)^* e^{-iE_{in}t} \right|^2$

$$V_{0\lambda}^i = \mathcal{N}_\lambda^{(i)}$$

KK-mixing of the 0-mode

- We assume all matrices to be **simultaneously diagonalisable**
- We derived **analytically, masses** and **mixings** for all cases
- **Constraints** from χ^2 using MINOS/MINOS+ and Daya Bay data

$$\mathcal{L} \supset -\overline{\nu_L} \begin{pmatrix} \chi_0 m_D & \chi_1 m_D & \chi_2 m_D & \dots & \chi_N m_D \\ 0 & \mu_{D,1} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \mu_{D,2} & \dots & 0 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & \mu_{D,N} \end{pmatrix} \nu_R$$

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$$\mu_n = n\mu_1$$

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